

MEDICAL ASTROLOGY - DIABETICS IN ASTROLOGY AND AYURVEDA

P. Rajakaladevi* & Dr. A. Kalaivani**

* Research Scholar, School of Vedic Astrology, Vels University, Pallavaram, Chennai, Tamilnadu

** Research Supervisor, School of Vedic Astrology, Vels University, Pallavaram, Chennai, Tamilnadu

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Introduction:

Both Astrology and Medicine were developed as a part of religion in ancient India. Astrological guidance was sought for, virtually, all day-to-day work, including taking of medicines for the remedies of ailments. Medicines were administered only at astrologically suitable times of the day. Following the medical and astrological principles, separately and together, was thus a way of life which even a laymen could afford to follow. The intellectuals accepted these principles through logic, the laymen through faith and devotion. The result was the same: a physically and mentally healthy society. The subject of Astrology is very deep, wide and technical and requires a life time for its successful study. It is fascinating for the common man. In Astrology the signs Aries etc. Have been considered as the "Head" of the Kala Purusha or time personified.

The sign Aries the first sign of the Zodiac, is the 1st limb of the Body, that is the "Head".

Taurus the 2nd sign Limb that is the face.

Gemini the 3rd sign is the 3rd limb, that is the Arms and the Respiratory Canal.

Cancer the 4th part is the Chest.

Leo the 5th sign is the fifth part, that is the Belly and the Heart.

Virgo the 6th sign is the 6th Limb, that is the intestine.

Libra the 7th sign is the 7th Limb, the private parts of the Body.

Scorpio is the 8th sign and it is the 8th part, the Scortem.

Sagittarius is the 9th sign and therefore the 9th part, that is the Hip.

Capricorn is the 10th sign and 10th Limb, that is the Knees.

Acquarius is the 11th sign and it represents the 11th part of the Limbs, that is the Legs.

Pisces is the 12th and the last sign represents the Limb of the Kala Purusha that is the feet. The affliction by the influence of malefic planets of any number of a sign along with its lord will bring injury or disease to the Limb.

While working on this short paper, I have considered the following working model points also.

- The seven planets from Sun to Saturn have control over the following minerals (Dhaathu) of human body.

Sun	-	Bones (Asthi)
Moon	-	Blood (Asruk or Raktha)
Mars	-	Bone Marrow (Majja)
Mercury	-	Skin (Thwak)
Jupiter	-	Adipose Tissues or Fats (Vasaa)
Venus	-	Semen/Sperm (Sukla)
Saturn	-	Muscles (Snayu)

- Mars represents the muscular system and Saturn represents muscular and skeletal systems (as per Western astrology).
- In Vedic Astrology Saturn is karaka for chronic diseases.
- Sixth house is considered as the house of diseases.
- Mars, karaka for muscles, is a planet of work and action and Saturn is responsible for the structure of the body.
- Rahu rules genetic diseases.
- Virgo is the 6th house (the house of disease) of the Kaala Purusha.
- A weak Jupiter which is also considered as life (jeeva)

Moreover, the following points are also taken note of.

- Venus aspected by Saturn or Mars cause to show symptoms of the disease.
- Lord of Sixth house, posited in 6th, 8th, 10th or 12th house and aspected by a malefic planet also causes the disease.
- Relationship of Maandi (Gulika) with the Rahu Ketu Axis.
- An ill-placed Mercury or Mercury aspected by a malefic planet is also a reason for this disease because Mercury governs the nervous system.

- A badly posited or a functional malefic Jupiter (the planet of expansion).
- Saturn aspecting either Aries or Scorpio (both houses owned by Mars).
- Weak Sun (representing Soul) and Moon (representing Blood).
- Mars posited in the 12th house.

Duration of Zodiac in Rasi:

To travel 30 degrees in one Rasi each planet takes the following number of days:

SUN	30 Days
MOON	2 Days
MARS	45 Days
MERCURY	27 Days
JUPITER	1 Year or Little Less
VENUS	30 Days
SATURN	30 months or 2 1/2 Years
RAHU	18 Months or 1 1/2 Years

Planets Karakas:

Each planet is designated to have effect on various relationships or attributes as follows:

SUN	Father
MOON	Mother
MARS	Younger Brothers or Sisters
MERCURY	Maternal Uncle, Education
JUPITER	Children, Elder Brother & Finance
VENUS	Wife or Husband
SATURN	Servants
RAHU	Maternal
KETHU	Paternal

Drekkanas:

Drekkana helps to analyse the general characteristics of a person. There are Four Groups.

- KROORA: Wicked minded, Wanderer engaged in sinful deeds, Quarrelsome.
- WATERY: Pleasure of Loving, Kind Hearted, getting wealth by agriculture or through Watery objects (fish), Large Bodies, Emotional.
- SOUMYA: Handsome, Kind Hearted, Prosperity, Happiness.
- MIXED: Bad Character, Extra Marital relations, Violate nature. Sources of death are predicted at the rising of 8th Bhava.

Bhava Karakathwas:

1st House	Sun
2nd House	Jupiter & Mercury
3rd House	Mars & Saturn
4th House	Moon, Venus & Mercury
5th House	Jupiter (Children), Mars (Wife's Brother)
6th House	Mars, Saturn & Mercury
7th House	Venus
8th House	Saturn
9th House	Jupiter (Fortune), Mars & Sun
10th House	Mercury, Sun, Saturn, Jupiter & Mars
11th House	Jupiter
12th House	Saturn & Venus

Auspicious and Inauspicious 12 Lagnas:

- Mesha Lagna: Guru, Ravi, and Kuja are auspicious. Shani, Budha and Sukra-ill disposed, Shani will give death to the native.
- Vrishabha Lagna: Shani is auspicious, Budha, Shukra and Ravi are beneficial, Guru, Kuja, Chandra are evil Planets.
- Mithuna Lagna: Shukra is the most beneficial with Budha and Shani gives excellent resul. Kuja, Guru and Ravi are evil.
- Kataka Lagna: Guru, Kuja and Chandra gives beneficial result, Kuja is the Raja Yoga Planet. Shukra, Budha and Shani are evil.
- Simha Lagna: Kuja, Guru and Ravi are auspicious, Guru, Kuja is favourable houses causes Raja yoga. Shani will not give death to a person but Budha with 2nd Lord with other evil Planet kills the person.
- Kanni Lagna: Shukra is Rajayoga Karaka. Budha, Shukra combined together causes Rajayoga. Kuja, Chandra, Guru and Ravi are evil Planets.

- Thula Lagna: Shani alone causes Raja Yoga. Budha and Shani produce benefics. Guru, Ravi and Kuja are inauspicious. Guru and Shukra in makara kills the native.
- Vrischika Lagna: Guru is beneficial. Kuja, Chandra and Ravi produce Raja Yogam. Budha, Shukra and Shani are evil.
- Dhanur Lagna: Kuja with Guru is good. Ravi and Kuja combination produce Raja Yogam. Shukra, Budha and Shani are evil.
- Makara Lagna: Shukra in conjunction with Budha produce Raja Yogam. Kuja, Guru, Ravi and Chandra are evil.
- Kumbha Lagna: Shukra produces Raja Yogam. Guru, Ravi, Kuja and Chandra are evil.
- Meena Lagna: Chandra and Kuja are auspicious. Kuja with Chandra or Guru causes Rajayoga. Shani, Shukra, Ravi and Budha are evil.

Sun as Rogakaaraka:

The contexts when Sun become disease causing planet in a horoscope are:

- When Sun is situated in Neecharaasi or sathru Rasi that is when Sun in a horoscope is in Thula, Makara, Kumbha and Vrishabha.
- When Sun is in Mruthyubhaaga or Kroora Shashtyamsa, in whichever Raasi or Bhava.
- When Sun in a Horoscope situated in the Constellation of Saturn and Venus.
- Sun in 6th, 8th and 12th Bhaavas.
- Sun receives the aspects, or is conjoined with Lords of 6,8,12 Bhaavas.
- When Sun becomes the Lord off 6th 8th or 2th Bhaavas.
- When Sun receives the aspectss or is conjoined with malefic planets, Paapagrahaas.
- When Sun becomes a maaraka (death causing planet) by the Lordships of 2nd or 7th Bhaava, or by occupying 2nd or 7th Bhaava.
- When Sun becomes a possessing planet (baadhaka) or situates in the sign of possession (Baadhaasthaana).
- When Sun is situated in the 22nd Drekkanna of the Lagna or Lord of the 22nd Drekkanna.

Moon as Rogakaarakas:

Diseases caused by Moon generally occur below the age 7. If Moon has no strength, the child would be short lived or would die suddenly. The occasion when the Moon is weak, there by becoming a diseases causing planet are explained below.

- When Moon situates in Vrischicka (Neecha Raasi).
- Moon in Mruthyubhaaga (death causing points) in any Raasi.
- Moon is weak from Ashtami thithi in new moon to Sapthami thithi in full moon every month.
- When there are malefic planets on either side of the moon in a horoscpe.
- When there are no planets on either side of moon this is known as Kemadruma Yoga.
- In horoscope when moon receives the aspects of malefic planet or when it is cojoined with malefic planet.
- When Moon occupies 6th 8th 12th Bhaava or receives the aspect of the Lords of 6th 8th or 12th Bhaava or Moon cojoins the Lord of 6th 8th or 12th Bhaava.
- When Moon becomes baadhaga or Maaraka (death causing).
- When Moon becomes the Lord of 22nd Drekkanna or occupies 22nd Drekkanna.
- In a horoscope shashtaashtama (6-8) or in dwidwadasa (2-12) positions of the Lord of the Mahadasa (main period) Kethu.

Mars as Rogakaaraga:

- When Mars in Neecha Raasi or enemical raasi (Mars in Kataga, Kanni or Mithuna).
- When Mars in 6,8,12 and 7 Bhaavas.
- When Mars is cojoined with or aspected by the Lords of 6,8,12.
- Mars becomes the Lord of 6,8,12 Bhaavas.
- Mars is the enemy of the Lord of the main Dasa.

Mercury (Budha) as Rogakaaraga:

- When Mercury occupies 6,8,12 houses.
- When Mercury is in between malefic planet.
- When Mercury is in conjunction of or aspected by the Lords of 6,8,12 houses.
- When Mercury is in the Stars of Moon namely Rohini, Atham and Thiruvonam.
- Mercury is in a Raasi in Mruthyubhaaga (death causing points).

Jupiter (Guru) as Rogakaaraga:

- When Jupiter is in Makara, Mithuna, Kanni, Vrishbha and Thulam raasis becomes weak.
- When in any Raasi Jupiter is in Mruthyubhaaga, (death causing).

- When Jupiter stands in 6,8,12 houses.
- When Jupiter stands in the Lord of 6, 8, 12 houses.
- When Jupiter cojoined with the Lords of 6,8,12 houses.

Venus (Sukra) as Rogakaaraga:

- When Venus in neecha raasi (Kani) or in enemical sign Simha owned by Sun or Kataka owned by Moon.
- When in any Raasi Venus is in Mruthyubhaaga, (death causing).
- When Venus is in 6,8,12 positions.
- When Venus stands in the Lord of 6, 8, 12 houses.
- When Venus cojoined with the Lords of 6,8,12 houses.

Saturn (Sani) as Rogakaaraga:

- When Sani in neecha raasi Meshha or in enemical sign Simha owned by Sun or Kataka owned by Moon Vrichiga owned by Mars.
- When in any Raasi Sani is in Mruthyubhaaga, (death causing).
- When Sani is in 6,8,12 positions.
- When Sani stands in the Lord of 6, 8, 12 houses.
- When Sani cojoined with the Lords of 6,8,12 houses.

Rahu as Rogakaaraga:

- Rahu in Vrischika raasi.
- Rahu in Conjunction with, Sun, Moon, Maandi (Gulika), Saturn.
- Raahu in Kataka or Simha.
- Raahu in 8, 12 house.
- Rahu in conjunction with 6,8,12 house Lords.

Kethu as Rogakaaraga:

- In a horoscope when Kethu is in Mithunan raasi or in Simha raasi.
- Persons whose Lagna is Meshha, Makara, Vrischika or Kataka.
- When Kethu is in conjunction with Moon, Venus or Saturn in a horoscope.
- When Kethu is in connection with 8, 12 houses or Lords of 6,8,12 houses.
- When Kethu moves through the 3, 5, 7 constellations from the star of the native.

In Western medicine (Modern medicine), the human body is studied in terms of systems or group of organs which work together. The organs in a system are grouped together because they are interconnected and also because they are made up of the same type of tissues.

Astrology and medicine are both ancient forms of knowledge in India:

Astrology and Medicine are inseparable, texts on ancient Indian Medicine contain references to planetary combinations causing specific diseases. Vedic Astrology is unique in another respect. It advocates remedial measures in the form of propitiation of planets in the event of an untoward planetary combination. There are three main systems of medicine today. The most prevalent is the Allopathic, which means treating an illness by producing results opposite to those produced by disease. It is based of sound scientific principles and has the greatest acceptance. Homeopathy is the other system which is based on the principles of treating an illness by a medicine which would normally produce the same results as the disease itself. The Ancient Indian system of medicine is known as Ayurveda, literally, "the science of Life" While many consider it as a separate system, it actually encompasses both Allopathy and Homeopathy. Astrology, Allopathy, Homeopathy and the present version of Ayurveda have all their role as well as their limitations. The wisest recourse lies in realizing the limitations of each and using them not as antagonistic but as complimentary to each other. Only thus can they be used to benefit humankind!

A medical Astrologer may consider the following factors while studying a chart with respect to disease.

- Timing of disease
- Diagnosis
- Severity
- Treatment

Timing or Onset of Disease:

This is a strong area of an Astrologer. A sound Astrologer, on examining a horoscope, should be able to indicate the time when a person is liable to fall ill. This may help in taking some preventive steps, the astrological remedial measures to forestall the malady. For the medical man, it is not possible to predict a future illness.

Diagnosis of the Disease (Nature):

This is a weak area for the astrologer. To be sound in this will require a lot of research by medical men proficient in astrology. Diagnosis of a disease is the strongest area of the medical man, with all sophisticated investigations at his disposal.

Severity of Disease (Outcome):

A patient or a consultant is naturally, concerned about the severity of an ailment and its outcome. A medical practitioner of today with his sound knowledge, will be able to accurately decipher the possible course that an ailment may take in a given patient. A good Astrologer, too, should be able to indicate the severity and outcome of an illness with a fair amount of accuracy, sometimes perhaps better than the medical practitioner.

Treatment:

There is no doubt that medical remedies of today are far superior to, and more reliable than, any astrological remedies. Astrology can, however help in two ways. Firstly, when adverse planetary influences indicate the occurrence of an ailment at a future date, and medical science understandably has no clue about it, resorting to propitiation of planets as a remedial astrological measure may be undertaken. Secondly, Astrology can sometimes indicate whether or not surgical intervention is going to help, and when. In addition, it is possible that a sound astrologer may be able to point to a diseased organ or region when the medical man is finding it difficult to locate the site of illness, without doubt this happens only infrequently. In conclusion, Medical Astrology of today is a relatively new subject. There are many challenging opportunities for research. The known basic principles of classical astrology have to be extended into the unknown areas of medical science. It is hoped that medical astrology would someday be of great help to the medical profession.

What is Diabetes:

Diabetes mellitus, commonly referred to simply as diabetes, is a metabolic disease that causes high blood sugar. The hormone insulin moves sugar from the blood into your cells to be stored or used for energy. With diabetes, your body either doesn't make enough insulin or can't effectively use the insulin it does make. Untreated high blood sugar from diabetes can damage your nerves, eyes, kidneys, and other organs. But educating yourself about diabetes and taking steps to prevent or manage it can help you protect your health.

Types of Diabetes:

There are a few different types of diabetes:

- Type 1: Type 1 diabetes is an autoimmune disease. The immune system attacks and destroys cells in the pancreas, where insulin is made. It's unclear what causes this attack.
- Type 2: Type 2 diabetes occurs when your body becomes resistant to insulin, and sugar builds up in your blood. It's the most common type—about 90% to 95% Trusted Source of people living with diabetes have type 2.
- Gestational: Gestational diabetes is high blood sugar during pregnancy. Insulin-blocking hormones produced by the placenta cause this type of diabetes.

A rare condition called diabetes insipidus is not related to diabetes mellitus, although it has a similar name. It's a different condition in which your kidneys remove too much fluid from your body. Each type of diabetes has unique symptoms, causes, and treatments. Virgo (6th House) Diseases connected with sixth house: Diabetes Hyper glycaemia which is excess of glucose (Sugar) in the blood .Glycosuria (sugar in Urine). The carbohydrates taken in are duly converted into glucose in intestine and from these are carried to liver for conversion into glycogen. This process of conversion from glucose to glycogen and from glycogen to glucose takes places by the action of a hormone called insulin .A gland called pancreas, Which is lying near the small intestine, provides this hormone .It produces insulin and discharge into duodenum, which is first's part of small intestine .

Diseases Connected with Sixth House (Virgo):

Diabetes mellitus is common disease in india carbohydrates taken in are duly converted to glucose in the intestine from there carried to liver for conversion. For this conversion insulin is a must. A gland called pancreas produces this insulin. Whenever there is a not utilized properly starts excreting in the urine and called polyuria. Excess of thirst and ingestion of water is called polydipsia. Jupiter rules the pancreas, the liver and carbohydrates. Affliction of Jupiter with Venus and Moon results in diabetes. Jupiter rules pancreas the liver and carbohydrates. The affliction of Jupiter along with Venus and moon results in diabetes.

- Venus moon Jupiter together with affliction of Virgo sign 6th house and lord of the 6th gives rise to diabetes 8th house also rules over the disease
- Mercury in Sagittarius or pisces aspected by sun native will suffer from urinary diseases
- Saturn Sun and venus in the 5th house causes diabetes.
- Mars in the 10th house Saturn or aspected by saturn causes diabetes.
- Sun in the ascendant Mars in the 6th causes diabetes.
- Ascendant aspected by malefic and venus in the 8th or Venus aspecting 8th house causes diabetes.
- Saturn and Rahu afflict Jupiter either by aspect or conjunction causes diabetes
- Combust Jupiter on Rahu Kethu axis results in Diabetes
- Jupiter in the constellation of Saturn causes diabetes
- When Saturn Afflicts the Moon creates diabetes
- Jupiter in Poorvashada constellation causes diabetes

- Cancer sign is afflicted by Saturn causes diabetes
- Jupiter in Rahu's constellation afflicted by Rahu causes diabetes.
- Moon and Jupiter afflicted by malefic posited in the 8th house causes diabetes
- Venus in 6th and Jupiter in 12th house causes diabetes
- Malefic in the ascendant with Venus and Jupiter results in diabetes
- Strong malefic in ascendent while Moon and Jupiter afflicted causes diabetes
- A Strong Malefic in 8th house and Venus and Jupiter afflicted causes diabetes.
- Venus in 8th House with malefic causes diabetes
- The Lord in 12th and 12th lord aspected by Jupiter causes diabetes.
- The 7th Being a watery sign occupied by the Sun, Saturn, Mars or Rahu results type I diabetes
- Jupiter in 6th 8th and 12th house causes diabetes
- Jupiter in 8th aspected by Saturn results in diabetes
- Venus with malefic in 6th 8th 12th houses results in diabetes
- Jupiter in 12th and Venus in 6th causes diabetes
- Jupiter Aspected by 6th or 12th lord causes diabetes
- Venus with malefic in ascendant causes diabetes
- Venus in 6th and Rahu in ascendant results diabetes
- Rahu with 8th lord in 5th 8th or 9th houses causes diabetes.

Diabetics in Ayurveda:

Ayurveda is an alternative medical system with historical roots in the Indian sub- continent. The Theory of practice of Ayurveda is Pseudoscientific. Ayurveda is heavily practiced in India and Nepal, where around 80 % of the population report using it. The main classical ayurveda texts begin with accounts of the transmission of medical knowledge from the God to Sages, and then to human Physicians. The printed editions of the Sushruta Samhita frame the work as the teachings of Dhanvantri Hindu God of Ayurveda incarnated as King Divodasa of Varanasi to a group of physicians including Susruta. Historical evidence for Ayurvedic texts terminology and concepts appears from the middle of the first millennium. In Ayurveda texts dosha balance is emphasized and suppressing natural urges is considered unhealthy and claimed to lead to illness. Ayurveda treatises describe 3 doshas namely, Vata, Pitta and Kapha, and state that balance of the doshas results in health while imbalance results in disease.

Types of Prameha in Ayurveda:

Diabetics in Ayurveda are divided into 20 types. They are based on Vata, Pitta and Kapha. Pramaham is the ayurvedic name for Diabetics.

In Kapha there are 10 types: Kaphajam:

- Udaka meham
- Ikshu meham
- Saandra meham
- Suramehm
- Pishta meham
- Shukrameham
- Sikatameham
- Sheetameham
- Shanairmeham
- Lalameham

In Pitta there are 6 types: Pittajam:

- Ksharameham
- Neelameham
- Kaalameham
- Haridrameham
- Manjishtameham
- Raktameham

In Vatta there are 4 types: Vatajam

- Vasaameham
- Majjameham
- Hastimejam
- Madhumeham

Treatment for Diabetic (Prameham) in Ayurveda:

Dealing with the treatment the text lists, Old Chaama, Koovaraga, Nauruvari, Wheat, Chennayari, Thuvara Paryaru and Horse Gram as beneficial for Diabetics (Prameham). Bitter tasting vegetables, Flesh of

animals inhabiting jungles, Flesh of Deer and Birds, Cooked Yavam, Green Gram, Navara and Chennella are also among the things that help cure Diabetics (Prameham). A Kashaayam made of Triphala, Devathaaram, Bark of Maramanjil and Muthanga Kizhangu, taken with honey will cure Diabetics (Prameham). Juice of crushed Gooseberry with powdered Varattumanjal or Triphala powder or Rock Fluid, taken with honey is a cure for Diabetics (Prameham).

Conclusion:

With the blessings of Poojya Swamiji and the systematic guidance from my Guide Dr. A. Kalaivani, I hope I can successfully complete my research work on time

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